

Design and Implementation of UART Serial Communication Module Based on FPGA

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Abstract—Designing a System-on-a-Chip (SoC) on the FPGA is now a trend in digital design because it gives a lot of advantages over discrete electronic based product such as higher speed, lower power consumption, smaller size, lower cost etc. UART (universal asynchronous receiver and transmitter) is a serial communication protocol. Basically this protocol is used to permit short distance, low cost and reliable full duplex communication. It is used to exchange data between the processor and peripherals. For reliable data transmission, serial communication is very effective than parallel communication when considering the cost as well as complexity of the system increases. To design a UART which is implemented with Verilog HDL can be easily integrated onto FPGA to achieve more reliable and error free data transmission. This paper presents the hardware implementation of UART using Verilog HDL on FPGA:EP2C20F484C7, family of Altera cyclone II. Simulation is done by Quartus II simulator which is fully compatible with UART.

Key words—UART, Verilog HDL, FPGA, SoC, Quartus II.

I. INTRODUCTION

FPGA or Field Programmable Gate Array is a type of logic chip that can be programmed. The FPGA configuration is generally specified using a hardware description language (HDL). FPGAs have programmable logic components called 'logic blocks' and a hierarchy or reconfigurable interconnects which facilitate the wiring of the blocks together[1]. Asynchronous serial communication can be implemented easily on FPGA.

Asynchronous serial communication is a popular, easy and successful method of sending and receiving data. This technology is usually implemented by UART. Universal Asynchronous Receiver Transmitter (UART) is a microchip with programming that controls a computer's interface to its attached serial devices[2]. The UART is basically used in between the slow and the fast peripheral devices for example: computer and printer or in between the controller and LCD [3]. This paper implements the core function of UART and integrates them into a FPGA chip. In our design, we have used FSM (finite state machine) so that the design of UART becomes more stable and reliable. The UART has mainly three parts which are transmitter, receiver and baud rate generator.

Transmitter sends data at specific clock rate. It first sends binary 0 as the start bit. The start bit is used to alert the receiver that a word of data is about to be sent and to force the clock in the receiver for synchronization with the clock in the transmitter[4]. Then it sends the data bits serially. After sending all data bits then it sends binary 1 as a stop bit. Stop bit alert the receiver that a word has been send completely. The time to take to send every bit must be equal. Figure 1 shows the frame format of UART.

Fig. 1. UART frame format

When receiver receives all bits it discards start bit and stop bit. Then it converts the serial data into parallel format.

Baud rate generator generates the clock frequency for transmitter and receiver at a specific baud rate. Our design has used 9600bps.

II. UART TRANSMITTER

Transmitter module converts the parallel data into serial bit stream. The architecture of the transmitter will consist of a controller, a data register (tx_datereg), a data shift register (tx_shiftreg) and a status register (bit_counter) to count the bits that are transmitted. The input signals are provided by the host processor and the output signals control the movement of data in the UART. The controller has the following inputs.

- *ready*: assert by the host machine to indicate that data bus has valid data.
- *t_byte*: transition of state to sending.
- *bit_counter*: counts the bit during transmission.

Controller forms the following output to control the datapath of transmitter.

- *load_shiftreg*: Assertion of *load_shiftreg* loads the contents of *tx_datereg* to *tx_shiftreg*.
- *clear*: clears *bit_counter*.

In our design of transmitter, finite state machine has been used. The transmitter state machine has three states.

A. idle

When the reset is asserted, machine enters in this state. It is also the default state. In this state two activities will occur.

- The contents of *tx_datereg* are loaded into *tx_shiftreg*, which contains 10 bits; LSB is the start bit and MSB is the stop bit and middle 8 bits are data bit.
- State transition from state idle to state waiting.

B. waiting

The machine remains in waiting state until the external processor asserts *t_byte*.

C. sending

At the sending state, the LSB of *tx_shiftreg* will be transmitted. The first transmitted bit is 0, which alerts the receiver of start of transmission. At the same time, the contents of *tx_shiftreg* are shifted toward LSB. As the data shift occurring, 1s are back-filled in *tx_shiftreg* and *bit_counter* is incremented. State remains in sending, while *bit_counter* is less than $[\text{word_size}+2]$. As the *bit_counter* reaches $[\text{word_size}+2]$, *clear* is driven to 1 indicating that all bits of augmented word have been shifted to serial output. At the next active edge clock, machine returns to idle.

In Fig. 2 state diagram of UART transmitter has been shown.

Fig. 2. State diagram of UART transmitter

The baud rate of a data communication system is the number of symbols per second transferred. A symbol may have more than two states, so it may represent more than one binary bit.

Baud rate generator is actually a kind of frequency divider. The baud rate frequency factor can be calculated according to a given system clock frequency and the required baud rate.

The frequency coefficient (M) i.e. count value of the baud rate generator is,

$$M = \frac{\text{System frequency}}{\text{Factor of baud rate} \times \text{baud rate}}$$

In our design, the system clock is 50 MHz and baud rate is 9600 bps. The output clock frequency of baud rate generator is $1 \times 9600\text{Hz}$.

$$\text{So, } M = \frac{50 \text{ MHz}}{1 \times 9600\text{Hz}} = 5208.333\dots$$

Here, the frequency coefficient M is not in round figure. To obtain the efficiency in FPGA, we rely on the fact that the serial interface can tolerate a few % of error in baud rate generator.

IV. UART RECEIVER

The UART receiver receives serial bit stream of data. Then it removes the start and stop bit and make the data in parallel format.

In our design, data will be sampled at a rate of baud rate generator determined by *sample_clock*, which is generated at the receiver's host. The cycle of the *sample_clock* will be counted to ensure that the data are sampled in the middle of a bit time. The sampling algorithm must verify:

- The start bit has been received properly.
- Generate sample.
- Load the data into local bus.

The arrival of the start bit will be determined by successive samples of value 0 after the input data goes low. Then three additional samples will be taken to confirm that a valid start bit is arrived. Thereafter 8 successive bits will be sampled at approximately centre of their bit times.

In our design, the receiver state machine has also three states: - idle, starting and receiving. Transitions between states are synchronized by *sample_clock*.

A. idle

Assertion of asynchronous active low reset put the machine in idle state. It is also the default state. It remains there until *data_in* is active low. If *data_in* is active high, the machine makes a transition to state starting.

B. starting

In starting state, the machine samples *data_in* to determine whether the first bit is valid start bit or not. If the bit is zero, then it is valid start bit, otherwise it is invalid. Depending on the sampled values, *inc_sample_counter* will be asserted which increment the value of counter. It also asserts

clr_sample_counter to clear the counter. If the next three samples of data_in is zero, the machine decides that the start bit is valid and makes a transition to the state receiving.

C. Receiving

In the receiving state, 8 samples are taken for 8 data bits. inc_sample_counter will be asserted here. Then bit_counter is incremented. If the sample bit is not the last bit, inc_bit_counter and shift are asserted. The assertion of shift will cause the sample value to be loaded into the MSB of rcv_shiftreg which is receiver shift register. It will also shift the 7 leftmost bits of the register towards the LSB. When all the bits have been sampled, load and ready_out are driven to 1. With assertion of load with logic high, the contents of receiver shiftreg will load into the data bus as a parallel word. Assertion of ready_out is the handshake output signal to the processor.

In Fig. 3 state diagram of UART receiver has been shown.

Fig. 3. State diagram of UART receiver

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

For simulation purposes, we use Quartus II software. Device is Altera cyclone II, FPGA: EP2C20F484C7. Simulations for transmitter and receiver are done separately.

A. Transmitter simulation

Figure 4 shows transmitter simulation where clock, reset, ready, t_byte are used as input node and data_out is used as output node which is the serial output of transmitter. Additional two nodes serial_test and sent_word are used as output node for inspection whether the data_out gives the desired value or not.

According to design, the transmitter clock frequency generated by baud rate generator is 9600Hz. Transmitter sends the ASCII value of “u” which is 75 in Hexadecimal value and in binary is (1110101)₂. sent_word shows that simulation is done successfully.

Fig. 4. Simulation result of transmitter

B. Receiver simulation

Figure 5 shows receiver simulation where serial_in, sample_clock, reset, ready_in used as input node, and rcv_datareg is used as output node. error1 and error2 ensure that the rcv_datareg provides the desired value.

In receiver simulation, receiver sample_clock frequency generated by baud rate generator is 9600Hz and the baud rate is 9600bps. The input value of receiver is the ASCII value of “u” which is 75 in Hexadecimal and in binary is (1110101)₂. rcv_datareg receives it successfully. The values of error1 and error2 are logic lows which ensure that simulation is error free.

Fig. 5. Simulation result of receiver

C. Schematic diagram of UART

Figure 6 shows the schematic diagram of UART.

Fig. 6. RTL Schematic diagram of UART

VI. IMPLEMENTATION

The proposed design is implemented on Altera cyclone II, FPGA: EP2C20F484C7. Table I shows the comparison of resources used between reference research[4] and our proposed design in the transmitter section where our design shown better result.

TABLE I. TRANSMITTER FLOW SUMMARY

Parameters	Proposed design	Reference research[4]
Logic elements	51(Out of 18,752)	78
Pins	5(Out of 315)	13

The total resources used in the receiver are also shown in the Table II.

TABLE II. RECEIVER FLOW SUMMARY

Parameters	Usage	Percentage
Logic elements	66(Out of 18,752)	<1%
Combinational functions	59(Out of 18,752)	<1%
Dedicated logic registers	40(Out of 18,752)	<1%
Registers	40	
Pins	15(Out of 315)	5%

The transmitted signal from rs-232 serial port of DE1 board is shown in figure 7. This signal is observed from oscilloscope which is much compatible for communicating with GSM

module. In future, this design will be implemented with full duplex serial communication by GSM module.

Fig. 7. Transmitted signal of UART

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper describes the architecture of UART and implemented this on the FPGA using Verilog description language to achieve reliable serial data communication. Function of UART has been tested using Quartus II simulator, Altera's Cyclone II family and FPGA chip EP2C20F484C7. We find the simulation results are reliable and stable. The design has great flexibility i.e. by error checking technique, we can detect different types of error occurred during communication and hence correct them, it also compatible with different baud rate. So, this design can effectively play a vital role in the SoC technology in upcoming year.

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